

A Review on the Lateral Pedicle Flap as a Treatment Modality For The Coverage of Millers Class 2 Gingival Recession

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Abstract

During 100 A.D. back, the only treatment modality that was most of the times carried out in the field of dentistry whether it was for a problem of carious tooth, mobile tooth (even for grade 1 or grade 2 mobility), receding gums, or extraction of the involved teeth. Often the extraction was a much traumatic one, and proper healing never took place. However now a days, dentistry has evolved so much that apart from extraction as a treatment modality, many other treatment are available. One of such treatment for receding gums is the lateral pedicle flap in which the adjacent teeth is used as a donor teeth to cover the receding teeth by the flap of the donor teeth.

Key Words: Extraction, recession, millers, root coverage, lateral pedicle flap.

Introduction

Long time ago, almost 100 A.D. back, dental field had a very limited treatment modality. In this treatment modality, the only treatment that was much of a prior concern was extraction of the diseased tooth; whether this diseased tooth has a pit, and fissure caries, class 1 caries, class 2 caries, grade 1 or grade 2 mobility, Millers class 1, or class 2 recession.¹ However over these past few years, dentistry had come so far beyond extraction that extraction can be considered a much last treatment modality.² Over these few years, people have become aware of their dental problems, and the point which is of prior concern in terms of patient point of view is esthetics and to save the diseased tooth.³ Considering esthetics as a prior concern as per patient point of view, which is one of the reason that dentistry had evolved so much beyond extraction. Now a days beyond extraction, smile designing, composites, veneers, other restorations, depigmentation, pedicle flaps, free gingival grafts are available, which tend to save the tooth instead of extracting them.⁴

Gingival Recession

In the field of Periodontology, four structures, are of important concern; gingiva (whose main function is the protection of the underlying structures), and the alveolar bone, cementum, and periodontal ligament (whose main function is to act as a supporting tissues for the teeth).⁵ Talking in terms of gin-

giva, so gingiva is the part of oral cavity, that covers the alveolar process of jaws, and surrounds the neck of tooth in a collar like fashion.⁶ Different characteristic features of gingiva are there, that gives the gingiva, its sole identity. One of the characteristic feature, that is position of the gingiva. The normal position of gingiva is at the level of cemento enamel junction, or 1mm coronal to the cemento enamel junction.⁷ However this position of gingiva is not stationary as compared to cemento enamel junction, which remains stationary throughout the life of an individual. This change of position can vary at the time of gingivitis or periodontitis and also after the different phases of treatment plan.⁸ However the treatment plan is considered to be successful as if all the signs and symptoms of gingivitis are eliminated and the gingiva returns to its normal colour, contour, consistency, surface texture, and position.⁹ Taking consideration into the position of gingiva, this gingival position can shift either more than 1mm coronal to the cemento enamel junction, a condition called as gingival enlargement, or there can be an apical shift in the position of gingiva, a condition called as gingival recession.¹⁰ However long back ago, gingival recession terminology, had been

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replaced by the term marginal soft tissue recession, which is defined as the displacement of soft tissue margin, apical to the cemento enamel junction with oral exposure of the root surface. Marginal soft tissue recession is the more appropriate term to be used than the gingival recession, as it involves the recession of either alveolar mucosa or gingiva. In terms of communication with the patient, the term root coverage is much more appropriate.¹¹

Causes of Gingival Recession

Gingival recession can be caused due to various reasons such as¹¹

1. Morphology: Morphology refers to the biotype of the Periodontium. This biotype is reflected in the gingiva as thin and scalloped, or thick and flat. The thin gingival biotype is identified by the prominence and visibility of roots beneath the gingiva and in case of thick gingival biotype, the roots are not so prominent and visible beneath the gingiva. This thin bio-type of gingiva shows that the bone beneath the gingiva is thin, and such type of bone had a higher chance of fenestration, dehiscence. This thin gingiva also has the tendency to tear during flap reflection. And henceforth concluding all these terms, this thin gingival biotype has a greater chance of recession.

The thick gingival biotype shows that the bone beneath the gingiva is thick and hence such type of bone resist the recession. But this type of bone has a greater chances of exostoses and tori. And henceforth considering all these things, the thick gingival biotype has a lesser chance for recession and in case if the recession occurs, then the prognosis is good to fair.

2. Trauma: Traumatic practice to the soft tissue can result in inflammation which often leads to the destruction of soft tissue, alveolar bone, cementum, and periodontal ligament. Following are some of traumatic things that can result in gingival recession.

A. Toothbrush: One of such traumatic injury the aggressive use of toothbrush. These type of individuals have a picture in their mind, that brushing vigorously can lead to a thorough cleaning of the teeth, often unaware that such type of tooth brushing is damaging their soft tissue, and leading to gingival recession. In such cases, its very necessary to identify the cause of gingival recession, because if these type of recession, treated by surgical intervention without a proper etiology for the recession can lead to a greater amount of recession after surgery. Often these aggressive toothbrush induced gingival recession is treated non-surgically.

B. Dental Floss: Often patients with a shallow probing depth and good periodontal health are conscious about keeping their teeth clean. And in the consciousness of keeping the teeth clean, these patients along with the toothbrush often use dental floss but this dental floss is often used in such a manner such that facial, papillar, and lingual gingival recession occur, because of a habit of keeping the dental floss in between teeth pushing hard

into the gingiva such that the gingival recession occurs.

C. Foreign Objects: It includes a habit of keeping the blunt end of a pen, pencil, fingernail on the gingiva and rubbing against gingiva leading to gingival recession. Another cause can be sports injury of the mouth leading to gingival recession.

D. Dental Procedures: Placement of rubberdam, gingival retraction cords, violation of biologic width by placement of subgingival margins of restoration can result in gingival recession.

3. Inflammatory Periodontal Disease: It results due to accumulation of plaque and calculus as an important etiological factors. Often there is loss of interdental bone and papillary height in the anterior region of dentition followed by lateral food impaction in the posterior region of dentition.

Millers Classification of Gingival Recession.¹²

Miller in the year, given the classification of gingival recession based upon the interdental bone loss, soft tissue loss, and the important landmark in millers classification was the muco-gingival junction.⁴

Class 1: Marginal tissue recession, that does not extend to the mucogingival junction. There is no soft tissue loss and the interdental bone loss.

Class 2: Marginal tissue recession that extends to or beyond the mucogingival junction. There is no soft tissue loss and the interdental bone loss.

Class 3: Marginal tissue recession that extends to or beyond the mucogingival junction. Loss of interdental bone or soft tissue is apical to the cemento enamel junction but coronal to the apical extent of the marginal tissue recession.

Class 4: Marginal tissue recession that extends beyond the mucogingival junction. Loss of interdental bone extends to the level apical to the extent of marginal tissue recession.

Fig. 1: Millers Classification of Gingival Recession.

Clinical Significance of Root Coverage/Gingival Recession Coverage

Since, gingival recession is characterized by the exposure of roots either partially or completely, this exposed root/roots holds the clinical significance that if these exposed root/roots are not covered by any type of root coverage procedures, then this exposure can lead to sensitivity / hypersensitivity, root caries, esthetically displeasing, and in some cases particularly in case of class 3 or class 4 gingival recession, decreased width of attached gingiva.¹³

Lateral Pedicle Flap

Surgical flaps used in the treatment of recession coverage are of two types:¹⁴

- 1. Pedicle Soft Tissue Graft Procedures:** These are the type of flaps, which maintain their connection with the donor site. Examples include: Coronal repositioning flap, lateral pedicle flap, semilunar flap.
- 2. Free Soft Tissue Graft Procedures:** These are the type of flaps, in which donor site in most of the cases is not the adjacent one, but a site such as palate from which graft is taken. Examples include: free gingival graft, connective tissue graft.

Term lateral pedicle flap was firstly introduced by Grupe and Warren in 1957. This technique uses the donor gingiva of a healthy adjacent tooth to cover the recessed tooth. It involves moving a full thickness flap to the mucogingival junction, after which a partial thickness flap is raised.¹⁵

Indications

1. A good indication for the use of lateral pedicle flap is an isolated area of recession, with no interproximal bone loss. Henceforth the use of lateral pedicle flaps achieve its good results in Millers class 1 or class 2 recession cases with 100 percent root coverage as compared to millers class 3 or class 4 cases where the chances of root coverage is 25 to 50%. The only condition to implement the lateral pedicle flap is that the adjacent donor tissue must have the sufficient width, and thickness of gingiva and vestibular depth with good bone thickness and no dehiscence or fenestration.¹⁵
2. The ideal indication is in a crowded teeth, where a donor tooth placed lingually has a sufficient thickness and width of gingiva, and the sufficient height and the thickness of bone and the adjacent tooth (Recipient tooth) is more facial and had little or no gingiva with root exposure.¹⁵

Contraindications

1. Significant loss of interproximal bone height¹⁵
2. Extensive root prominences¹⁵
3. Presence of extensive erosion or abrasion¹⁵
4. Presence of deep interproximal pockets.¹⁵

Advantages

1. Good vascularity of the pedicle flap as the pedicle flap get its blood supply from the base of flap.¹⁵
2. One surgical site hence one surgical wound which reduces the chances of bleeding and postoperative pain.¹⁵
3. A good technique to cover the isolated root recession.¹⁵

Disadvantages

1. Possibility of recession at the donor site.¹⁵
2. Possibility of occurrence of dehiscence and fenestration at the donor site.¹⁵
3. Not much applicable in case of multiple recession cases.¹⁵
4. Technique is limited by the sufficient amount of keratinized gingiva at the donor site.¹⁵

Procedure of Lateral Pedicle Flap

1. The first step is to determine the bone level at the facial aspect of the donor site after profound local anaesthesia. This distance of bone level from cemento enamel junction should not exceed more than 1-2 mm.¹⁵
2. Proper smoothing of recipient root should be carried out in order to eradicate any roughness ,and irregularities on the root surface as these irregularities and roughness will interfere with the proper adaptation of the flap, as well hampers the blood supply to the flap.¹⁵
3. The first incision is an oblique incision which is made at a distal end of a donor teeth beyond the mucogingival junction.¹⁵
4. This incision is continued as a sulcular incision from a donor teeth to a recipient teeth.
5. The third incision is a horizontal incision into the papilla between the recipient teeth and a non donor teeth and is terminated by a oblique incision beyond the mucogingival junction.¹⁵
6. Later on a full thickness flap is raised by a blunt dissection by a periosteal elevator and a partial thickness flap is reflected by a sharp dissection.¹⁵
7. The elevated flap is rotated from the donor teeth to a recipient teeth and is adapted by means of sutures.¹⁵

Fig. 1: Preoperative

Fig. 2: Incisions of View of Millers Lateral Pedicle flap Class 2 gingival recession.

Fig. 3: Flap stabilized by Means of Sutures.

Fig. 4. 6 Weeks Post Operative

View of 100% Root Coverage Common Reasons for The Failure of Lateral Pedicle Flap

1. Flap is not adequately stabilized because of tension present in the flap.¹⁵
2. Design of the pedicle flap is too narrow.¹⁵
3. Bone exposure because of poor flap adaptation or stabilization, resulting in occurrence of fenestration or dehiscence.¹⁵
4. Poor stabilization resulting in excessive movement of flap.¹⁵

Discussion

The field of Periodontology mainly revolve around two conditions; gingivitis and Periodontitis. The differentiating feature between gingivitis and Periodontitis is the loss of attachment as in case of gingivitis there is an inflammation of the gingiva but without the loss of clinical attachment. Once there is an extension of inflammation from gingiva into the bone, there is a clinical attachment loss and this condition is termed as Periodontitis.⁵ Apart from clinical attachment loss as a one of the characteristic clinical feature of periodontitis, a periodontitis is also characterized by other features such as in the sulcus depth which is termed as periodontal pocket, mobility, furcation involvement, bone loss, and recession.⁶ So here this review is on the recession also known as root coverage in terms of patients language and the lateral pedicle flap as a procedure to cover the recession. In the normal individual, there is a position at which the gingival level remains in health within the oral cavity, once this position gets altered by any means such as by aggressive tooth brushing, flossing, rubbing blunt end of pen, pencil against the gingiva, the retention of etiological factors plaque and calculus on the gingiva can all lead to the

inflammation and shift in a position of the gingiva to a more apical level which in a clinical term is known as gingival recession or a more appropriate term marginal soft tissue recession as this later term includes the loss of both the soft tissue and the bone.¹¹ Various treatment modalities to cover up this recession or the exposed roots are there, out of which the one which we have written our review is on the lateral pedicle flap or lateral repositioning of the flap. This lateral pedicle flap is best suited for the teeth with isolated recession as in case of multiple recession defects it is quite difficult to move the flap laterally. Lateral pedicle flap has the donor site and the recipient sites adjacent to each other. These adjacent areas has the advantage of being less traumatic to the patient, less bleeding postoperatively and a good blood supply from the base of the flap. However the limitation of lateral pedicle flap is that the tooth which act as a donor for a recessed tooth should have a sufficient width, thickness, adequate height of the interproximal bone and there should not be any bone loss, because if we choose such a donor tooth with insufficient thickness and width of gingiva, as well bone loss facially and interproximally can lead to recession of the donor tooth, without the proper root coverage of the recipient tooth because of the hindrance with the blood supply from the base of the flap.¹⁵ Thus keeping these conditions in the mind, lateral pedicle flap is best suitable for Millers class 1 or class 2 recession cases where the chances for root coverage is 100% in most of the class 1 or class 2 recession cases and is less suitable for millers class 3 or class 4 recession cases, where due to the loss of bone both interproximally and facially and insufficient gingival width and thickness, the chances of root coverage reduces from 100% to 25-50%.¹⁵

Summary and Conclusion

Recession or the root exposure is one of the pathology that needs to be of a thorough concern to the patient. Patient must be made aware about their exposure of roots, the consequences of it and various treatment modalities available to cover those exposed roots. The cause of recession must be identified and treated accordingly. It is the duty of the clinician to diagnose and emphasized the importance of root coverage to the patient so that in order to achieve a 100 percent chances of root coverage.

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